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Entrepreneurship And The Economic Empowerment Of Women In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to examine the dynamics of entrepreneurship and its contribution to the economic empowerment of women in Delta State, Nigeria. It focused on examining key indicators such as the establishment of women-owned businesses, participation in entrepreneurial activities, and access to critical business resources through a gender-specific initiative supporting small business growth. The study utilized a survey design and employed a 5-point Likert scale questionnaire to collect data. A purposive sampling approach was employed in selecting 1,044 female business owners across Delta State. Regression modeling was employed to test the hypotheses using a 0.05 alpha level. The results indicated a significant enhancement of women-owned businesses on economic empowerment, with 0.000 as p-value and 56.929 as the t-statistics. Additionally, women's involvement in entrepreneurial pursuits was shown to exert a strong influence on their economic empowerment, reflected by a p-value of 0.000 and a t-statistic of 111.895. Furthermore, access to critical business resources was found to have a substantial effect on economic empowerment, as evidenced by a p-value of 0.000 and a t-statistic of 71.543. These results underscore the pivotal role of women-led businesses, entrepreneurial participation, and resource availability in driving both economic and social empowerment for women in Delta State. The investigation determined that entrepreneurship plays a critical role in enhancing the economic empowerment of women in Delta State. Women-led businesses, active participation in entrepreneurship, and access to resources significantly contribute to their economic and social advancement. The study recommends that policymakers and stakeholders implement supportive measures to enhance the success of women-led businesses. These include: Streamlining registration procedures for businesses, providing tax incentives for female entrepreneurs & establishing targeted funding options to improve access to critical business resources.

Keywords: Access to Business Resources, Economic Empowerment, Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial Participation, Women-Owned Businesses,

INTRODUCTION

Women's empowerment plays a crucial role in fostering peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable societies (Moyo & Dhliwayo, 2019). Entrepreneurship serves as a powerful tool for women to harness their potential, contributing significantly to their economic well-being and positively impacting their communities and nations (Raghunandan, 2018). The increasing presence of women-owned businesses globally is having a transformative effect on innovation, wealth generation, and job creation in both advanced and less-developed nations (Noguera *et al.*, 2013). Agarwal (2018) emphasizes that increasing women's economic opportunities and access to resources leads to beneficial ripple effects across families and communities. Economic empowerment is essential for empowering women to make informed decisions that impact their socioeconomic circumstances (O'Donnell *et al.*, 2021). Beyond personal success, economic empowerment facilitates higher participation in the workforce, thereby contributing to broader economic growth (Jayachandran, 2021; Hendriks, 2019; Kapoor, 2019).

Women's empowerment spans several key areas, including education, finance, politics, and skills acquisition. Education empowers women by fostering knowledge and skill development, creating avenues for income generation (Forgeard, 2022). Political empowerment encourages women's involvement in governance, ensuring equality and the protection of their rights (Mahbub, 2021). Financial empowerment strengthens women's ability to manage resources effectively, making informed decisions that help achieve personal goals (Consumers and Business Affairs, 2022). Skill-based empowerment enhances women's earning potential, supports families, and boosts self-confidence (Vyas, 2018). Economic empowerment, which encompasses education, training, and skills development, enables women to become self-reliant, increase productivity, and generate income (Seven Women, 2020). These dimensions are vital for women striving to succeed in entrepreneurship.

Entrepreneurship entails utilizing one's skills to seize opportunities within dynamic economic, social, and political environments to generate income (Kumar & Singh, 2021). Despite its potential, gender disparities continue to limit women's access to entrepreneurial opportunities (Costa *et al.*, 2016; Rossi *et al.*, 2011). To foster female entrepreneurship, a supportive labor market and societal acknowledgment of women's contributions are essential (Dautović *et al.*, 2019). Research by Onu (2021) and Karwati *et al.* (2018) underscores how women's entrepreneurial efforts contribute to economic stability and empowerment within families. Female entrepreneurship also promotes self-sufficiency, with Tanti *et al.* (2021) emphasizing the critical role of mentorship and global connections for women entrepreneurs. Social networks play an essential role in helping women balance business and family commitments (Ayatakshi-Endow & Steele, 2021).

Despite women accounting for nearly half the population in Nigeria, they encounter barriers that hinder their full participation in entrepreneurship due to inadequate empowerment (Ali & Salisu, 2019). Addressing these barriers requires government intervention to promote gender equality, expand business opportunities, and create a more inclusive economic environment. Empowering women through education, skill development, and better access to finance will allow them to invest in businesses, explore new markets, and expand their services, thus contributing to national economic growth. Despite their potential, female entrepreneurs in Nigeria continue to face significant challenges, including persistent gender inequalities that impede the development and viability of their enterprises.

Statement of the problem

The issue of empowering women through entrepreneurship in Delta State highlights a gap between the ideal—equal access to resources—and the reality faced by many women. Ideally, women should be provided with adequate support, funding, and training to manage businesses that promote financial independence and contribute to community development. However, in Delta State, women encounter substantial obstacles including inadequate access to capital, inadequate training, and gender-based discrimination, which undermine their ability to succeed in business and achieve economic independence. These challenges perpetuate financial dependence, reduce job creation, and hinder local economic growth, leaving the state's development potential largely untapped. A gender-sensitive approach is essential to addressing these barriers and unlocking the complete realization of women's contributions to

socioeconomic advancement. This research investigates how enhanced resource accessibility and support for women-led businesses can foster economic empowerment and small business development in Delta State.

Objectives of the investigation

This study primarily studied how entrepreneurship contributes to the economic empowerment of women, with a particular emphasis on gender-targeted initiatives designed to promote small business development in Delta State. The specific intentions of the investigation were:

- i. To evaluate the impact of women-owned businesses on the economic empowerment of women in Delta State.
- ii. To examine how women's contribution to entrepreneurial pursuits influences their economic empowerment in Delta State.
- iii. To analyze the contribution of access to business resources in shaping women's economic empowerment in Delta State.

Research questions

Consistent with the goals of the study, these research questions were developed:

- i. To what extent do businesses owned by women contribute to women's economic empowerment in Delta State?
- ii. How does women's engagement in entrepreneurship affect their economic empowerment in Delta State?
- iii. In what ways does access to business resources influence women's economic empowerment in Delta State?

Research hypotheses

In accordance with the research objectives, these hypotheses have been proposed for examination:

- Ho₁: There is no significant influence of women-led enterprises on women's economic empowerment in Delta State.
- Ho₂: Participation in entrepreneurship by women does not significantly contribute to their economic empowerment in Delta State.
- Ho₃: Women's access to entrepreneurial resources does not meaningfully affect their economic empowerment in Delta State.

Scope and limitations of the study

This research focuses on three central components: women-owned enterprises, entrepreneurial participation, and access to essential business resources, all recognized as critical drivers of economic empowerment. Conducted in Delta State, Nigeria, the study examines how supporting women entrepreneurs can improve livelihoods and stimulate local economic growth. By analyzing the experiences, obstacles, and successes of female entrepreneurs in Delta State, the research provides targeted insights valuable for stakeholders pursuing gender-inclusive economic strategies in similar settings.

However, the study acknowledges certain limitations. It evaluates economic empowerment through broader entrepreneurial dimensions rather than specific measurable indicators, which may constrain the depth of insight into particular outcomes. Its geographic concentration on Delta State may limit the relevance of the outcomes to other locations, as socio-economic contexts differ across regions. Moreover, the exclusive focus on women entrepreneurs overlooks broader systemic factors affecting entrepreneurship. Despite these constraints, the study contributes valuable, context-specific insights and serves as a foundation for implementing gender-targeted initiatives in comparable regions.

Review of Related Literature

Entrepreneurship

Women's entrepreneurship is a transformative factor that fosters economic expansion and social development by enabling women to establish, manage, and grow businesses. Women play a critical role in MSMEs, being essential components of economic infrastructures globally. These enterprises constitute

over 97% of businesses, contribute approximately 60% to GDP, and provide 94% of employment (Mayoux, 2001; Ndubusi, 2004). Ranging from home-based ventures to formal enterprises, MSMEs allow women to balance family and professional responsibilities. Beyond economic contributions, women-led MSMEs enhance social cohesion by raising household incomes and promoting community stability. Globally, women entrepreneurs significantly impact the economy, with women producing over 80% of food in sub-Saharan Africa and similar high figures across Asia, North Africa, and Latin America, underscoring their importance in food security and sustainable development (Ali & Ali, 2013).

Economic pressures act as "push" motivators for female business owners, and "pull" factors, including aspirations for financial independence and self-fulfillment. Through their entrepreneurial efforts, women create jobs, establish local supply chains, and generate a "multiplier effect" that boosts community-level economic resilience. Women's businesses support local economies by fostering partnerships and expanding supply networks. Scaling these businesses not only challenges societal norms but also fosters gender equality, empowering women in household and community decision-making. By developing accessible ecosystems that include resources, training, and funding, female entrepreneurs drive development in a sustainable manner and demonstrate the power of inclusive economic policies to drive growth and equity globally.

Women-owned businesses

Women-owned businesses are enterprises predominantly managed, operated, and controlled by women (Brush, 2014). These ventures range from informal small-scale operations to well-established firms in diverse industries. A recent GEM report highlights the global rise of women's entrepreneurship, with around 163 million women engaged in business activities across 67 economies (Kelley *et al.*, 2020). This growth stresses the value of gender in entrepreneurship. However, female entrepreneurs face challenges like limited access to financial resources, professional connections, and business backing, which restrict their growth potential (Ahl, 2006). Studies reveal that women-owned businesses often exhibit slower revenue growth and lower survival rates compared to their male counterparts (Robb & Watson, 2012).

Women-owned businesses come in different structures, such as corporations, sole proprietorships and partnerships, spanning industries like services, manufacturing, and agriculture (Minniti & Naude, 2010). Female entrepreneurs leverage their skills, experiences, and networks to align their businesses with personal expertise and interests. The advancement and sustainability of female-owned businesses are influenced by cultural, social, and economic factors (Welter & Smallbone, 2011). Providing targeted support, such as access to training, mentorship, and funding, is crucial for addressing these challenges. Governments and organizations play a vital role in fostering ecosystems that enable women entrepreneurs to thrive, ensuring that their contributions to economic growth and social progress are fully realized.

Women's contribution to entrepreneurial pursuits

Women's involvement in entrepreneurial pursuits encompasses their participation in the establishment, management, and expansion of enterprises (Brush, 2014). This engagement spans aspects such as entrepreneurial mindset, business creation, and ownership. According to Kelley *et al.* (2017), women's entrepreneurial endeavors are shaped by factors like education, training, and financial accessibility. Nevertheless, they encounter distinct obstacles, including cultural norms, societal biases, and limited networks (Ahl, 2006). Despite these challenges, there is a notable global shift with women pursuing entrepreneurship, greatly impacting job creation and economic progress (Minniti, 2010). Women entrepreneurs are active in micro-enterprises, small businesses, and socially driven ventures. Gundry *et al.* (2014) emphasized that women-led enterprises frequently integrate social and environmental objectives with financial goals, fostering innovative and sustainable business approaches. The entrepreneurial ecosystem, which includes supportive policies, mentorship, funding opportunities, and incubation programs, plays an active role in overcoming the barriers faced by women entrepreneurs and fostering their success (Brush *et al.*, 2018). Building such an ecosystem is essential for enabling women's entrepreneurial potential and ensuring their impactful participation in economic activities.

Access to business resources

Access to business resources pertains to the ability of entrepreneurs to obtain the tools and support necessary for business growth and operations (Brush *et al.*, 2018). These resources include financial capital, technology, human capital, networks, and institutional backing. Shane and Venkataraman (2000) identified resource accessibility as pivotal for entrepreneurial success. Within a resource-based framework, possessing and effectively deploying these resources enhances competitive advantage and business strategy development (Barney, 1991). Resource availability is driven by factors like institutional structures, social networks, and the broader entrepreneurial ecosystem (Stam, 2015). Autio and Acs (2010) highlighted the ecosystem's role in determining the accessibility of critical inputs, while institutional factors, including laws and societal norms, either enable or constrain resource availability (North, 1990). Scott and Davis (2007) underscored the impact of institutional rules on the conduct of business and the cost of resource acquisition, emphasizing the interconnectedness of institutional frameworks and entrepreneurial development.

Women economic empowerment

Empowerment is the approach by which groups or individuals gain the ability to make decisions, pursue chosen paths, and take actions aligned with their goals for a meaningful life (World Bank, 2001). In relation to women, empowerment represents a complex change that allows them to take control of their lives and choices (Kabeer, 2001). Advancing women's empowerment is integral to upholding women's rights and achieving gender equity (Cornwall, 2016). Worldwide, empowering women economically is key to driving sustainable development and inclusive progress, as it helps reduce poverty and drives community-level social change (Bayeh, 2016). Gender-biased norms and policies restrict productivity and personal growth for women and men, but women are disadvantageously affected by barriers that hinder their economic engagement (Bayeh, 2016). In conflict-affected or economically unstable regions, gender-sensitive policies face challenges such as resource shortages, weak infrastructure, and competing development priorities, requiring collaborative efforts among stakeholders (Bruck *et al.*, 2011).

Empowering women in such difficult settings necessitates active participation from civil society, non-governmental organizations, and development agencies (Datzberger & Nguyen, 2018). Initiatives aimed at reducing gender gaps through economic empowerment, often termed "smart economics," utilize businesses as catalysts for societal transformation (Roberts & Soederberg, 2012). Promoting gender equality enhances productivity, strengthens future development prospects, and improves institutional resilience (Nandan & Mallick, 2020). When women gain control over financial resources, they contribute to national economic growth by reallocating household spending to benefit child welfare (Anderson *et al.*, 2021). Sustainable empowerment is anchored in fostering women's confidence and independence, which can be achieved through education, entrepreneurial ventures, and skill development (Cornwall, 2016). Attaining gender equality also requires improving market systems, expanding women's role in the employment sector, and enhancing private-sector engagement (Baud, 2016). However, fragile environments pose significant hurdles to achieving these goals (UN, 2014).

Theoretical Framework

Social capital theory

Social Capital Theory, developed by Pierre Bourdieu in the 1980s, puts a spotlight on the importance of social networks, relationships, and connections as support that foster economic and social advancement. Bourdieu characterized social capital as a complement to economic and cultural capital, facilitating access to opportunities and resources through trust and mutual exchange within networks. This theory is especially applicable to women entrepreneurs, as social networks facilitate access to mentorship, funding, and other critical resources necessary for business success. For women in Delta State, leveraging social capital can address challenges such as inadequate funding and limited expertise, enhancing economic empowerment and entrepreneurial sustainability.

Critics of Social Capital Theory argue that its benefits are unevenly distributed, often favoring those in higher societal positions, thereby perpetuating existing inequalities (Portes, 1998; Lin, 2001). In

patriarchal contexts, women may not derive the same advantages from social networks as men, given restrictive cultural norms. Moreover, scholars caution against overemphasizing social capital, noting the equal importance of tangible assets such as financial capital and legal frameworks for achieving economic progress.

This study adopts Social Capital Theory to examine how women in Delta State can leverage networks to navigate entrepreneurial barriers, such as restricted funding and limited training opportunities. By engaging in strategic networks, women entrepreneurs can access mentorship, share resources, and establish connections that facilitate market entry and sustainability. This approach not only strengthens their businesses but also contributes to broader economic and societal development, showcasing the transformative potential of social capital in fostering inclusive entrepreneurship.

Empirical Reviews

Koirala *et al.* (2024) investigated the role of female entrepreneurship in promoting empowerment within Nepal's Gorkha District, with a focus on aspects such as decision-making, financial independence, societal views, income generation, and employment creation. Their analysis, based on a purposive sample of 150 female entrepreneurs and employing partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM), revealed that empowerment is significantly enhanced through improved decision-making abilities, job creation, and higher income levels, emphasizing the importance of fostering these factors for women's empowerment. In Oyo State, Ahmed *et al.* (2024) studied how small and medium enterprises (SMEs) empower women, particularly female proprietors engaged in agriculture. They found that SMEs help women achieve financial independence and improve literacy, enabling them to allocate resources toward essential needs like education and healthcare. Their recommendations included increasing support for SMEs, offering specialized training programs, and enhancing market networks to further strengthen women's empowerment. Sule *et al.* (2024) explored how SMEs empower women in Oyo State, using cluster sampling to collect data from 283 participants. Analyzing their findings through descriptive and inferential statistics, they reported that 77% of respondents experienced improved financial stability and personal empowerment. Their results also highlighted strong support for government initiatives aimed at enhancing women's socio-economic status.

Odebode *et al.* (2023) examined how women's empowerment influences entrepreneurship growth in Lagos State, Nigeria. Their survey of 111 women showed a strong correlation between empowerment and entrepreneurial activity. Using descriptive statistics and Chi-Square analysis, they demonstrated that women's empowerment significantly increases their participation in entrepreneurship, reinforcing the value of initiatives promoting empowerment. In Gombe State, Bello *et al.* (2023) assessed the impact of empowerment programs, such as anchor borrower schemes, on SME performance. Their study, involving 260 SMEs, concluded that such programs positively influence SME growth. They recommended expanding access to similar empowerment schemes to support SMEs across various sectors and enhance their overall contributions. Mohd-Nor and Ali (2022) explored women's empowerment through entrepreneurship in Boko Haram-affected areas of Northeast Nigeria. Through interviews with 23 women, the study highlighted the dual challenges and opportunities for empowerment in conflict-affected regions, showing that while obstacles persist, such circumstances also create unique avenues for women to gain empowerment.

Nguse *et al.* (2022) analyzed the role of financial inclusion in fostering empowerment among Ethiopian women in SMEs. Using a mixed-methods approach with data from 324 women-owned SMEs, they found that financial inclusion, supported by favourable government policies and regulations are instrumental in strengthening women's economic empowerment. Jacob *et al.* (2022) studied micro-enterprises and their influence on women's empowerment in Kerala, India, using data from 384 participants in the Kudumbashree Mission. Employing confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling, they found a strong link between women's empowerment and economic development, affirming the role of micro-enterprises in empowering women. Riaz and Chaudhry (2021) examined the contributions of SMEs to women's empowerment and poverty alleviation in Southern Punjab. They highlighted education, skill

development, and SME involvement as key drivers of poverty reduction. Their recommendations included expanding opportunities for women through enhanced education and employment initiatives. Mohammad et al. (2020) assessed how regulatory frameworks and training programs support women's empowerment through entrepreneurship. Surveying 397 female entrepreneurs, they found that entrepreneurship significantly improves women's economic and social status, highlighting the importance of development programs within the SME sector. Gouranga et al. (2020) investigated the motivations and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. Their study identified critical factors that drive entrepreneurship and highlighted the problems to achieving sustainable development goals (SDGs), emphasizing the need for supportive measures. Islam (2020) explored how women's entrepreneurship development advances empowerment in Bangladesh. Through multivariate analysis, the study underscored the role of factors such as education, regulatory frameworks, and support networks in empowering women, with SMEs playing a pivotal role in this process.

Obun-Andy (2019) reviewed how entrepreneurship contributes to women's empowerment and economic growth in Nigeria. The study emphasized the societal advantages of empowering women entrepreneurs, particularly in enhancing economic contributions. Ab-Rahim and Mohamed (2019) examined how youth empowerment moderates the relationship between SMEs and poverty in Niger State, Nigeria. Their findings highlighted that SME participation promotes job creation, skill development, and income growth, significantly improving socio-economic outcomes. Esiebugie et al. (2018) explored how women's empowerment drives entrepreneurial development in Benue State, Nigeria. Their findings highlighted strong associations between education, job creation, and financial stability, emphasizing the role of empowerment in promoting entrepreneurial growth. Ekechukwu et al. (2018) studied the impact of mandatory entrepreneurship courses in Nigerian universities on preparing students for business creation. They found that these courses equip students with essential skills and attitudes, empowering them to contribute to economic development through entrepreneurship. Obadeyi et al. (2017) investigated the role of entrepreneurship in empowering women in Ogun State, Nigeria. Their findings highlighted that addressing gender disparities and increasing resource access can significantly empower women, fostering overall socio-economic development.

METHODS

Design

A survey design was employed to provide a structured approach for collecting data representative of a larger population. This design enabled the study to gather detailed information on variables such as attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors using a structured questionnaire, complemented with interviews when necessary. The study focused on female-owned small businesses in Delta State, encompassing sectors such as retail, manufacturing, and services. This varied population allowed for comprehensive insights into the entrepreneurial landscape and the distinct barriers experienced by women entrepreneurs in the region. The Cochran formula was used to calculate the sample size, ideal for populations considered to be infinite. The computation process ensured a representative sample for accurate data analysis.

$$n = \frac{[Z^2 * p * (1-p)]}{E^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

Z = Z-score corresponding to desired confidence level (1.96 for 95% confidence)

p = estimated proportion (0.5 for maximum variability)

E = margin of error (0.03 for 3%)

Substituting the values:

$$n = \frac{[(1.96)^2 * 0.5 * (1-0.5)]}{(0.03)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(3.8416 * 0.25)}{0.0009}$$

$$n = \frac{0.9604}{0.0009}$$

$$n \approx 1067.11$$

Round up to the nearest whole number:

$$n \approx 1068$$

So, the needed sample size is roughly 1068.

The research employed a purposive sampling technique, selecting participants based on their relevance to the study's objectives. Unlike random sampling, purposive sampling involves judgment-based participant selection, which can introduce some bias but ensures alignment with the study's focus on specific characteristics.

Data collection

Primary data were gathered firsthand from the selected participants, ensuring the study captured authentic and representative experiences of female entrepreneurs in the region. A predefined questionnaire functioned as the principal method for collecting data. Distributed personally to participants, it featured a 5-point Likert scale ranging from strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD), designed to elicit detailed responses aligned with the study objectives. The questionnaire's validity (both face and content) was confirmed to ensure it accurately measured the intended constructs. Reliability testing verified the instrument's consistency in measuring variables over time. The study used Cronbach's Alpha, with a coefficient above 0.7 considered satisfactory. A reliability analysis returned a Cronbach's Alpha figure of 0.933, reflecting excellent internal consistency.

Table 3.1: Reliability Table

Women's economic empowerment through Entrepreneurship: A Gender-focused Initiative for Small Business Development in Delta State	No of Items	Cronbach Alpha (CA) Coefficient
Women-owned businesses (WOB)	4	0.932
Women's Engagement in Entrepreneurial Activities (WEEA)	4	0.930
Access to business resources (ABR)	4	0.932
Economic Empowerment (EEM)	4	0.933

Source: Computation by Researcher (2024)

The Cronbach Alpha test values, ranging between 0 and 1, indicated strong reliability with an achieved value of 0.933, surpassing the acceptable threshold of 0.7.

After data collection, responses were scrutinized for completeness and prepared for statistical analysis. The linear regression was conducted using the SPSS version 27.0, with results presented in tabular form for clarity.

The study utilized the linear regression models to assess the causal relationship between the predictor variables and economic empowerment. The models were specified as:

$$EEM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WOB + \mu \tag{i}$$

$$EEM = \beta_0 + \beta_2 WEER + \mu \tag{ii}$$

$$EEM = \beta_0 + \beta_3 ABR + \mu \tag{iii}$$

Where;

EEM = Economic Empowerment

WOB = Women-owned Businesses

WEER = Women's Engagement in Entrepreneurial Activities

ABR = Access to Business Resources

β_0 = Intercept or regression constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Regression coefficients to be estimated for firm i in period t

μ = Stochastic error term.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Ho₁: Women-owned businesses have no significant effect on women's economic empowerment in Delta State.

Table 4.1 Simple Linear Regression Result1

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-value	Remark	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-ratio
Constant	.438	10.470	.000	Significant			
WOBB	.841	56.929	.000	Significant	.757	.756	3240.905

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

The analysis revealed an R-squared value of 0.757, indicating that 75.7% of the variation in economic empowerment is attributed to women-operated businesses. The F-statistic of 3240.905 and a p-value of 0.000 denote a significant relationship, while the t-statistic of 56.929 confirms a positive impact. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, supporting the alternative hypothesis.

Ho₂: Women's participation in entrepreneurship does not significantly influence their economic empowerment in Delta State.

Table 4.2 Simple Linear Regression Result2

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-value	Remark	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-ratio
Constant	.022	.866	.387	Insignificant			
WEERRR	.990	111.895	.000	Significant	.923	.923	12520.534

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

The regression analysis demonstrated an R-squared value of 0.923, meaning that 92.3% of the variation in economic empowerment is explained by entrepreneurial involvement. The F-statistic of 12520.534, p-value of 0.000, and t-statistic of 111.895 strongly indicate a significant relationship, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in favor of the alternative.

Ho₃: Access to business resources does not have a significant impact on women's economic empowerment in Delta State.

Table 4.3 Simple Linear Regression Result1

Variable	Beta (β)	t-Stat.	P-value	Remark	R ²	Adjusted R ²	F-ratio
Constant	.128	3.400	.001	Significant			
ABBRR	.942	71.543	.000	Significant	.831	.831	5118.390

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2024)

The results revealed an R-squared value of 0.831, showing that 83.1% of the variation in economic empowerment is due to access to business resources. The significant F-statistic of 5118.390, p-value of 0.000, and t-statistic of 71.543 confirm a positive and significant effect. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, supporting the alternative hypothesis.

DISCUSSION

The findings from the first hypothesis indicate that women-owned businesses substantially contribute to women's economic empowerment in Delta State. Women operating their businesses achieve financial independence and enhance their decision-making capacity, leading to improved social and economic standing. These outcomes empower women to manage resources effectively and actively contribute to their families and communities. This conclusion aligns with research conducted by Koirala *et al.* (2024) and Ahmed *et al.* (2024).

The second hypothesis underscores that women's active participation in entrepreneurial activities significantly enhances their economic empowerment. Women engaged in entrepreneurship acquire financial benefits, greater autonomy, and improved social status, while developing critical skills and accessing valuable networks that help them overcome traditional barriers. These results corroborate

findings from Sule *et al.* (2024), Odebode *et al.* (2023), and Bello *et al.* (2023), which highlight the transformative role of entrepreneurship in women's lives.

The third hypothesis reveals that access to business resources, including financing, training, and networking, is vital for advancing women's economic empowerment. Adequate resources enable women to expand their ventures, overcome challenges, and achieve sustainable growth. These findings are consistent with studies by Mohd-Nor and Ali (2022) and Jacob *et al.* (2022), which emphasize the significance of resource availability in promoting entrepreneurship among women.

Implication

The study highlights significant implications for policy and development. Policymakers are encouraged to design strategic actions that enhance women's access to entrepreneurial resources, such as funding, training, and mentorship, to foster economic growth and reduce poverty in Delta State. Supporting women-led businesses contributes to job creation, increased financial independence, and broader social benefits, including reduced gender inequality and enhanced community development. These efforts align with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 5 (Gender Equality) and Goal 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study provides robust evidence that women-owned businesses, entrepreneurial engagement, and access to resources significantly contribute to women's economic empowerment in Delta State. Women managing businesses attain financial independence, enabling them to make autonomous decisions and uplift their social and economic positions. Engagement in entrepreneurship equips them with critical skills and access to networks that foster economic resilience. Moreover, resource availability, including funding and training, enhances their ability to expand businesses and navigate market challenges effectively. These findings emphasize the transformative power of entrepreneurship and access to resources in empowering women economically and socially in Delta State.

Considering the findings, the following suggestions are recommended:

- a). Policymakers and stakeholders should implement supportive measures to enhance women-owned businesses in Delta State. Simplifying registration processes, offering tax incentives, and providing targeted grants will encourage business development among women in Delta State.
- b). Increased participation of women in entrepreneurship should be encouraged through mentorship, skills acquisition programs, and targeted training to improve their entrepreneurial expertise and knowledge in Delta State.
- c). Improving women's access to essential business resources, such as low-interest loans, startup grants, and networking opportunities, is crucial in Delta State. Collaboration with financial institutions and the establishment of support structures will ensure equitable access to these resources.

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Author contributions

A.J. is the primary author, responsible for writing the paper and contributing to its revisions. F.I.O. conceived the project, developed the survey, and established project partnerships. F.E.O. initiated several project collaborations and assisted in writing and revising the paper. F.E.A. organized and performed the data analysis for the article and compiled the results section. R.A.I. played a role in the conceptualization, survey design, data collection, project management, and manuscript revisions.

Conflict of interest statement

The author(s) declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Consent to participate

All respondents gave their consent to the survey exercise.

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REFERENCES

1. Ab-Rahim, R. & Mohamed, M. (2019). The relationship between small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and poverty in Nigeria. *Asia Proceedings of Social Sciences*, 5(1), 58–63.
2. Agarwal, B. (2018). Gender equality, food security and the sustainable development goals. *Current opinion in environmental sustainability*, 34, 26-32.
3. Ahl, H. (2006). Why research on women entrepreneurship needs to take a different direction. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 595-621.
4. Ahmed, S., Magaji, S., Ahmad, A. & Yunusa, A. (2024). From savings to empowerment: how women leverage SMEs in Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 23(5), 34-40.
5. Ali, A. & Ali, A. (2013). Challenges and constraints faced by Somali women entrepreneurs in Benadir Region. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 5(2), 411-436.
6. Ali, M. (2016). An assessment of factors affecting women participation in trade union activities in Yobe State, Nigeria. *Administration and Development*, 6(1), 236-252.
7. Ali, M. and Salisu, Y. (2019). Women entrepreneurship and empowerment strategy for national development. *Journal of Economics, Management and Trade*, 1-27.
8. Anderson, C., Reynolds, T., Biscaye, P., Patwardhan, V. & Schmidt, C. (2021). Economic benefits of empowering women in agriculture: Assumptions and evidence. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 57(2), 193-208.
9. Ayatakshi-Endow, S. & Steele, J. (2021). Striving for Balance: Women entrepreneurs in Brazil, their multiple gendered roles and covid-19. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship* 13(2): 121–141.
10. Baud, I. (2016). Moving towards inclusive development? Recent views on inequalities, frugal innovations, urban geo-technologies, gender, and hybrid governance. *The European Journal of Development Research*, 28(2), 119-129.
11. Bayeh, E. (2016). The role of empowering women and achieving gender equality to the sustainable development of Ethiopia. *Pacific Science Review for Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 37-42.
12. Bello, A., Musa, M. & Salisu, M. (2023). Effect of empowerment programmes on the performance of small and medium enterprises (SMES) in Gombe State. *Yobe Journal of Economics*, 8(1), 72-87.
13. Brush, C. (2014). Entrepreneurship theory and practice. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 17(2), 11-24.
14. Brush, C. & Cooper, S. (2012). Female entrepreneurship and economic development: An international perspective. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 24(1-2), 1-6.
15. Consumers & Business Affairs (2022). Financial empowerment tips. Retrieved, November, 15, 2024 from <https://dcba.lacounty.gov>.
16. Cornwall, A. (2016). Women's empowerment: What works? *Journal of International Development*, 28(3), 342-359.
17. Costa, C., Zelia, B., Fiona, E., Marilia, D. & Isabel, P. (2016). Through the gender looking-glass: Brazilian tourism entrepreneurs. *International Journal of Gender and Entrepreneurship* 8, 282–306.

18. Datzberger, S. & Nguyen, T. (2018). Deconstructing civil society actors and functions: On the limitations of international frameworks for fragile states. *Social Sciences*, 7(2), 30-37.
19. Dautovi'c, E., Nemša, O. & Sanja, L. (2019). Analysis of women entrepreneurship in Montenegro. *Knowledge International Journal*, 31, 1251–1257.
20. Ekechukwu, L., Nwinyinya, E., Okorie, G. & Albi-Oparaoch, F. (2018). The role of entrepreneurship education on the empowerment of Nigerian youths for national economic development. *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 36(3), 493-498.
21. Esiebugie, U., Richard, A. & Fabian, H. (2018). Women empowerment and entrepreneurship development in Benue State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 10(33), 138-153.
22. Estrin, S. & Mickiewicz, T. (2011). Institutions and female entrepreneurship. *Small Business Economics*, 37(4), 397-415.
23. Forgeard, V. (2022) How does education empower a person? Retrieved, November, 15, 2024 from <https://brilliantio.com>
24. Gouranga, C., Shanjida, C., Sunjida, K. & Tamanna, S. (2020). Achieving sustainable development through entrepreneurship & economic empowerment of women in the technological era. *International Journal of Management*, 11(9), 1385-1398.
25. Hassan, H., Abu, E. & Ibrahim, A. (2022). The impact of women's empowerment on their entrepreneurship intention in the Saudi food industry. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management* 15(571), 2-14.
26. Hendriks, S. (2019). The role of financial inclusion in driving women's economic empowerment. *Development in Practice*, 29(8), 1029-1038.
27. International Labour Organisation (ILO). (2003). *Small and medium enterprise development, globalization and gender briefs series*. IFP/SEED, 3. Retrieved, November, 18, 2024 from <http://www.ilo.org>
28. Islam, N (2020). Women empowerment through entrepreneurship development in Bangladesh: A multivariate analysis. *International Journal of Management*, 11(10), 20-29.
29. Jayachandran, S. (2021). Social norms as a barrier to women's employment in developing countries. *IMF Economic Review*, 69(3), 576-595.
30. Kabeer, N. (2001). Reflections on the measurement of women's empowerment. In discussing women's empowerment-theory and practice. *Sida studies No. 3*. Stockholm: Novum Grafiska AB.
31. Kapoor, S. (2019). Entrepreneurship for economic and social empowerment of women: A case study of a self-help credit program in Nithari Village, Noida, India. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 13(2), 123-142.
32. Karwati, L., Ansori, A., & Dinno, M. (2018). Women empowerment to build entrepreneurship. *Journal of Nonformal Education*, 4, 169–176.
33. Kelley, D., Baumer, B. & Baron, R. (2020). *2020 Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) report*.
34. Koirala, S., Gyanwali, S. & Ranabhat, D. (2024). Empowerment of Women through Entrepreneurship in Gorkha District, Nepal. *Intelligence Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(1), 61-72.
35. Kumar, N. & Singh, L. (2021). Status of Women-Entrepreneur in Indian Startups. *International Journal of Engineering Technology and Management Sciences*, 5, 1–12.
36. Mahbub, M. (2021). Women empowerment, theory, practice, process, and importance. Retrieved, November 21, 2024 from <https://www.researchgate.net>
37. Mayoux, L. (2001). Jobs, gender and small enterprises: Getting the policy environment right. An ILO working paper on a series on women's entrepreneurship development and gender in enterprises.

38. Minniti, M. & Naude, W. (2010). What do we know about the patterns and determinants of female entrepreneurship across the world? *The European Journal of Development Research*, 22(3), 277-293.
39. Mohammad, S., Haripada, B. & Nazrul, I. (2020). Women empowerment through entrepreneurship development in Bangladesh: A multivariate analysis. *International Journal of Management*, 11(10), 379-392.
40. Mohd-Nor, R. & Ali, A. (2022). Women empowerment through entrepreneurship in violent-conflict settings: Challenges and opportunities. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 12(8), 698 – 716.
41. Moyo, T. & Dhliwayo, R. (2019). Achieving gender equality and women's empowerment in Sub-Saharan Africa: Lessons from the experience of selected countries. *Journal of Developing Societies*, 35(2), 256-281.
42. Nandan, A. & Mallick, H. (2020). Does gender equality matter for regional growth and income inequality? An empirical analysis for the Indian states. *Journal of International Development*, 32(4), 439-469.
43. Nguse T., Desalegn G., Oshora, B., Tangl A., Nathan R. & Fekete-Farkasne M. (2022). Enhancing women economic empowerment through financial inclusion: Evidence from SMEs in Ethiopia. *Polish Journal of Management Studies*, 25(1), 270-291
44. Noguera, M., Alvarez, C. & Urbano, D. (2013). Socio-cultural factors and female entrepreneurship. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 9(2), 183- 197.
45. Obadeyi, J., Oba- Abimbola, A. & Oladejo, O. (2017). Women entrepreneurship development and women empowerment in Abeokuta South Local Government, Ogun State. 1st Covenant University International Conference on Entrepreneurship. 533-545.
46. Obun-Andy, M. (2019). Women empowerment through entrepreneurship development: A vehicle for economic growth in Nigeria. 1st National Conference of WITED, Ilaro Chapter. The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro. 95-103.
47. Odebode, O., Salisu, O. & Ajaegbu, N. (2023). The role of women empowerment in the development of women entrepreneurship in Lagos State. *Covenant Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 7(2), 59-68.
48. O'Donnell, M., Buvinic, M., Kenny, C., Bourgault, S. & Yang, G. (2021). Promoting women's economic empowerment in the covid-19 context. Washington, DC: Center for Global Development.
49. Onu, S. (2021). Entrepreneurship skill for empowering women in cocoyam production in Abia and Imo States, Nigeria. *Research on World Agricultural Economy*, 2, 20–25.
50. Raghunandan, V. (2018). Changing equations: Empowerment, entrepreneurship, and the welfare of women. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 19(3), 187-198.
51. Riaz, A. & Chaudhry, B. (2021). Role of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in women empowerment and poverty alleviation in Punjab, Pakistan. *International Journal Agricultural Extension*, 9(3). 439- 449
52. Robb, A. & Watson, J. (2012). Women and entrepreneurship: A comparative study of the United States and Australia. *Journal of Developmental Entrepreneurship*, 17(2), 1250005.
53. Roberts, A. & Soederberg, S. (2012). Gender equality as smart economics? A critique of the 2012 World Development Report. *Third World Quarterly*, 33(5), 949-968.
54. Rossi, M., Marie, S. & Silna, B. (2011). Women entrepreneurs in Switzerland: Situation, characteristics, motivation and entrepreneurial behaviour of women entrepreneurs in Switzerland. Paper presented at the 4th Annual Euromed Conference of the Euromed Academy of Business: Business Research Challenges in a Turbulent Era, Elounda, Greece, October 20–21.
55. Seven Women (2020). What is economic empowerment? Retrieved, November 21, 2024 from <https://sevenwomen.org>

56. Sule M., Ibrahim M., Abdullahi I. A. (2024), Impact of small and medium-scale enterprises on women's empowerment in Nigeria. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*, 7(2), 83-98.
57. Tanti, D., Robert, J., Ponco, B., Soekmawati, F. and Viviantie, S. (2021). Empowering cross-border women entrepreneurs via mobile ICT: Framework for Malaysian and Indonesian women-led MSMEs. *Journal of Nusantara Studies*, 6, 340–57.
58. Tende, S. (2016). The Impact of women entrepreneurs towards national development. *Information and Knowledge Management Journal*, 6(6), 1-12
59. UN. (2014). Gender Equality and Sustainable Development: World survey on the role of women in development. United Nations Publication.
60. Vyas, A. (2018). The impact of skill development on women empowerment. *International Journal of Research and Development*, 3(1),8-11
61. Welter, F. & Smallbone, D. (2011). Institutional perspectives on entrepreneurial behavior in challenging environments. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 49(1), 107-125.
62. World Bank. (2001). *World development report 2000/2001: attacking poverty*. New York: Oxford University.